

MODERN AND INTERNATIONAL PRINCIPLES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

¹Berdinazarov Zafar, ²Jabborov Shavkat

¹Dr. Tashkent International University, ²Alfraganus University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11090847>

Abstract. *The main goal of this article is to identify the most important policy directions, action plans and important factors in order to implement modern and international principles of tourism in Uzbekistan and to develop suggestions and recommendations for the effective use of these principles.*

Keywords: *modern and international principles, travel and tourism.*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi O'zbekistonda turizmning zamonaviy va xalqaro tamoyillarini hayotga tatbiq etish bo'yicha eng muhim siyosat yo'nalishlari, chora-tadbirlar rejalari va muhim omillarni aniqlash hamda ushbu tamoyillardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.*

Kalit so'zlar: *zamonaviy va xalqaro tamoyillar, sayohat va turizm.*

Аннотация. *Основная цель данной статьи определить наиболее важные направления политики, планы действий и важные факторы для реализации современных и международных принципов туризма в Узбекистане, а также разработать предложения и рекомендации по эффективному использованию этих принципов.*

Ключевые слова: *современные и международные принципы, путешествие и туризм.*

The strategy of tourism development in Uzbekistan is aimed at creating a unique tourist experience, attracting foreign and local tourists, and increasing the economic well-being of the country. For this reason, government of Uzbekistan has a clear of vision, mission, policy direction and action plan in order to implement modern and international principles of tourism in Uzbekistan. Such a modern and international principles include: ensuring environmental sustainability, social sustainability and economic sustainability. A central claim of modernity principles is that economic development, cultural change, and political change go together in coherent, and to some extent, predictable patterns.

According to this aim and strategy at the session of the General Assembly of the UN World Tourism Organization which held in Samarkand in October 2023, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev took the initiative to declare 2027 as the "International Year of Sustainable and Viable Tourism" in order to ensure the stability and flexibility of the tourism sector in the face of new problems and modern threats. On February 26 of this year this initiative was unanimously approved by the General Assembly of the Organization.

The resolution affirms the principles that tourism plays an important role in preserving the rich cultural heritage of different civilizations, strengthening peace and tolerance, and respecting the values of peoples. Special attention is paid to the development of "green" tourism in order to preserve ecology, biodiversity and reduce atmospheric pollution.

The document emphasizes the importance of developing sustainable tourism, including ecotourism, which serves to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, economic growth, full employment, development of rural areas, and improvement of the living conditions of rural residents. The resolution recommends that all stakeholders actively promote sustainable and viable tourism as an important tool to alleviate poverty, promote the participation of women, youth, the

elderly and persons with disabilities, expand economic opportunities, and create decent jobs and sources of income.

The President in his speech gave information about the major reforms being carried out in the field of tourism, such as “We are placing priority to the tourism sector in our “open doors policy”. We have granted a visa-free regime to the nationals of around one hundred countries. A simplified electronic visa system has been introduced for the nationals of 55 other countries as well. We have created favorable conditions for doing business in all subsectors of tourism. We have provided tax and customs benefits and strengthened credit and financial support. The subsidies are being allocated for the construction of new hotels, and attraction of international brands, as well as to increase the tourist flows. Thanks to this, despite the pandemic restrictions, we have implemented 800 infrastructure projects in two years. Over \$1 billion have been invested in improving tourism infrastructure in the city of Samarkand alone. The “Ipak Yuli” Tourist Center, which is hosting today’s forum is one of these large projects. In addition, the tourist police have been established to ensure the safety and security of tourists. The “Amirsoy” winter resort, the "Valley of Legends", "Zomin" and "Chorvok" zones have become international tourist destinations, attracting the attention of many foreign visitors. The number of hotel beds has reached 140 thousand, 70 new tourist routes have been launched, and 6 private airlines have begun operating in order to ensure favorable conditions for tourists. The number of foreign tourists traveling to Uzbekistan has doubled. Revenues from tourist exports have increased 4 times. For example, this year the number of tourists from Japan has increased 5 times, from India and Italy - 3.5 times, from the United States - 2 times. According to estimates, a total of 7 million tourists will visit our country by the end of this year. By 2030, we intend to increase this figure to 15 million and domestic tourist flow to 25 million”.

Current Travel and Tourism (T&T) industry of the country. Key contribution facts (2023 forecast): the direct contribution of T&T to GDP in 2022 was UZS9,750.6 bn (1.2% of total GDP). This primarily reflects the economic activity generated by industries such as hotels, travel agents, airlines and other passenger transportation services (excluding commuter services). But it also includes, for example, the activities of the restaurant and leisure industries directly supported by tourists. The direct contribution of T&T to GDP is expected to grow by 7.2% pa to UZS22,569.4 bn (1.5% of GDP) from 2023 to 2033. The total contribution of T&T to GDP (including wider effects from investment, the supply chain and induced income impacts was UZS26,645.0 bn in 2022 (3.4% of GDP). It is forecast to rise by 7.4% pa to UZS62,716.8bn from 2023 to 2033 (4.2% of GDP).

Employment direct contribution. T&T generated 226,470 jobs directly in 2022 (1.6% of total employment). This includes employment by hotels, travel agents, airlines and other passenger transportation services (excluding commuter services). It also includes, for example, the activities of the restaurant and leisure industries directly supported by tourists. By 2033, T&T will account for 290,885 jobs directly (1.8% of total employment), an increase of 2.3% pa from 2023. The total contribution of T&T to employment (including wider effects from investment, the supply chain and induced income impacts, see page 3) was 714,454 jobs in 2022 (5.2% of total employment). By 2033, T&T is forecast to support 902,008 jobs (5.7% of total employment), an increase of 2.4% pa since 2023.

Visitor exports contribution. In 2022, Uzbekistan generated UZS9,965.4 bn in visitor exports. By 2033, international tourist arrivals are forecast to total 10,574,000, generating expenditure of UZS23,095.1bn, an increase of 7.0% pa since 2023. T&T is expected to have

attracted capital investment of UZ\$4,108.5bn in 2022. T&T share of total national investment is expected to be 1.5% in 2033.

Economic contribution. Leisure travel spending (inbound and domestic) generated 86.9% of total internal spending in 2022 (UZ\$18,875.0bn) compared with 13.1% for business travel spending (UZ\$2,854.0bn). Leisure travel spending is expected to rise by 6.6% pa to UZ\$40,361.9bn from 2023 to 2033. Business travel spending is expected to rise by 9.6% pa to UZ\$9,718.2bn from 2023 to 2033.

Domestic travel spending generated 54.1% (UZ\$11,763.6bn) of total internal spending in 2022 compared with 45.9% (UZ\$9,965.4bn) for visitor exports (ie foreign visitor spending or international tourism receipts). Domestic travel spending is expected to rise by 7.2% pa to UZ\$26,985.0bn from 2023 to 2033. Visitor exports are expected to rise by 7.0% pa to UZ\$23,095.1bn from 2023 to 2033.

Our large-scale efforts are being recognized by the international community. In particular, Uzbekistan is ranked in the list of “the fastest growing tourist destinations” by the World Tourism Organization, and takes the leading positions in the list of “the safest country for tourism” of the famous social survey company Gallup. In addition, our country won in the nominations “Discovery of the Year” and “Gastronomic Tourism” of the U.S. magazine “National Geographic Traveler”. Last year, Uzbekistan was recognized as “the strongest tourist destination” in the “Global Muslim Tourism Index”.

Taking into account big changes and reforms realizing in tourism sector and effectively setup modern and international principles of tourism development in the country we have set big goals and plans for ourselves, and in this respect we are committed to closely working UNWTO and with our distinguish partners of the world. We are developing a 2030 Strategy for Comprehensive Development of Tourism. In this context, we will attach priority to the creation of modern tourist and transport infrastructure as a key direction.

Six more high-speed trains will be commissioned on the routes “Tashkent – Samarkand” and “Navoiy – Bukhara”, and 600 kilometers of additional railroads will be built. A high-speed train will run an-route “Tashkent-Khiva” from 2025, and this route will be extended to the city of Nukus by 2026. In addition, “Tashkent-Samarkand” and “Tashkent-Andijan” toll roads will be built on a PPP basis. As a result, the time of reaching the destination on these routes will be halved. By 2030, we will add 56 modern aircraft to our fleet and increase the number of jets to 100. In addition, the number of flights will increase by 4 times.

The “Open Sky” regime will be introduced in all airports, six major airports in the regions will be renovated on PPP basis. In addition, 30 major tourism clusters will be set up in each major city and tourist destinations. Today, there are more than 8 thousand cultural heritage sites in Uzbekistan. Over 200 of our tangible and 6 intangible sites are included in the UNESCO World Cultural Heritage List. As part of the national program “Masterpieces of Ancient History”: the number of cultural heritage sites attracting tourists will be increased from 800 to 2.5 thousand; 745 cultural heritage sites will be restored; “open-air museums” will be set up in 20 monuments.

As part of the Ziyarat (Pilgrimage) Tourism Program, we will increase the number of visitors three-fold. The magnificent architectural complex constructed in Samarkand in memory of our religious scholar Imam Bukhari will be one of our major projects in this regard.

The creation of joint tourist routes with the countries of our region, the expansion of transport and logistics capacities in Central Asia, including the implementation of the “One Tour, Entire Region” program, are at the core of our focus. In a word, we aim to create at least one

million new jobs in the future through our work on developing medical, ecological, gastronomic, ethno, extreme and other types of tourism.

So far, all achievements and aims above mentioned is not fulfill our goals in order to relize modern and international principles of tourism development in Uzbekistan, the global travel and tourism attractiveness and contributions always require changes and reforms in tourism policy strategies of the countries and make them to colloborate and comprehensively deepen their relations each other. We would like to make the following proposals in this direction:

First, wide spreading the 12 principles of sustainable tourism in the country, as recognized by the UNWTO, which are the concerned economic feasibility, local prosperity, employment quality, social equity, local control, cultural prosperity, visitor fulfillment, physical integrity, resource efficiency, biological diversity and environmental purity.

Second, according to the above mentioned principles the most pressing issue for the world tourism sector is to ensure a guaranteed system of tourists' security. The conflicts and instability observed in different regions of the world, today have detrimental effect on the development on the sector even more than the pandemic. Considering the current complex situation, in order to consolidate the firm legal framework in the international tourism sector, its necessary to adopt Global Safe Tourism Code under the guidance of the United Nations.

Third, in the era of increasing climate change, the adoption of the International Program of Action for the development of Green Tourism is more urgent than ever. It would be appropriate to establish the nomination "The Best City Promoting Green Tourism" within the Organization.

Fourth, it is expedient to establish a Council of Historical Cities for Tourism under the WTO. This platform allows to increase the flow of tourists to cultural heritage sites, exchange the best practices in the preservation of historical monuments, and develop recommendations and effective solutions.

REFERENCES

1. Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization (<https://president.uz/en/lists/view/6763>)
2. WTTC. Travel and Tourism Economic impact 2023, Uzbekistan, pp.4-6.
3. The same source, p.7.
4. Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization (<https://president.uz/en/lists/view/6763>)
5. Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization (<https://president.uz/en/lists/view/6763>)